

EMIC-ETIC PERSPECTIVE ON THE V-M-O REALIZATION OF THE SCHOOL OF EDUCATION, ARELLANO UNIVERSITY- PASAY CAMPUS

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ABSTRACT

The vision, mission, and objectives (VMO) of an educational institution form the cornerstone of its operations, guiding its academic programs and initiatives. The effective realization of these statements hinges on the institution's structure and the extent to which both internal and external stakeholders understand and embrace their essence. This study aims to assess the degree of realization of the VMO statements from both an internal (EMIC) and external (ETIC) perspective, focusing on understanding behaviors and personalities. Utilizing a descriptive research design, data collection, analysis, and tabulation were conducted to capture the prevailing perspectives of the respondents. The findings indicate that the Vision-Mission-Objectives of Arellano University were either fully realized or largely realized, with no evidence suggesting a lack of realization from the EMIC-ETIC perspective. Consequently, there were no significant differences observed in the respondents' perspectives, indicating a consistent understanding and alignment with the VMO of Arellano University. However, the study highlights the need for enhanced communication and engagement to reinforce the vision and mission of the School of Education, Arellano University. It emphasizes the importance of inclusive activities involving all stakeholders and adequate funding to ensure the sustainability of these efforts.

Keywords: *emic-etic, vision, mission, objectives, academic programs*

INTRODUCTION

The vision, mission, and objectives (VMO) serve as the foundation of any educational institution. The VMO statements set the direction of the various academic programs and activities of the school.

The vision and mission are statements on the long-term view of the institution of itself and of the world within which it operates, including the fundamental purpose of its existence, its long-term role and stature, and what it does to achieve this purpose and how it would like to play its role. The program educational objectives are broad statements that describe the career and professional accomplishments that the program is preparing graduates to achieve within three to five years of graduation. These objectives are based on the needs of the program's constituencies (CMO No. 37, 2012).

The realization of the University's VMO depends in its structure and stakeholders' assimilation on its essence as the main driving force of the whole organization. It is indeed deemed necessary that both the internal and external stakeholders gain a full grasp of understanding of the University's VMO statements. According to the study of Lucero (2010), the faculty and student participants have a high level of awareness of the University Vision, as well as its perceived congruency, appreciation, agreement, involvement, and responsibility on the VMGO.

Numerous studies regarding the VMGO have been conducted in recent years. A study has shown that the stakeholders such students and professors of a university are aware of its vision, mission, goals, and objectives and that these students and professors understand and accept these statements, along with the responsibility of realizing such objectives in their own capacities (Castillo, 2014). Another study has similarly concluded that the constituents of a university are aware and keen in knowing the importance of the core principles contained in their VMGOs (Salom& Florendo, 2013). Parents/alumni and other stakeholders have a high level of awareness, acceptance, and comprehension of the university's VMGO (Manapsal, 2016).

This study determines the extent of realization of the VMO statements from the EMIC-ETIC perspective. EMIC and ETIC approaches intend to understand behavior and personality. The EMIC approach investigates how local people think. How stakeholders perceive and categorize the world, their rules for behavior, what has meaning for them. An EMIC view of culture is ultimately a perspective focus on the intrinsic cultural distinctions that are meaningful to the members of a given society, often considered to be an 'insider's' perspective. While an ETIC view of a culture is the perspective of an outsider looking in. As Vetadine (2010) emphasizes, schools are inclined to be more successful in gaining in-depth learning when leaders collaborate with workers and the community to create a clear collective educational vision.

Research Questions

To give light to the problem, the researchers sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of realization of the V-M-O from EMIC-ETIC perspective?
 2. Will there be significance in their perspectives of V-M-O in case there is absence of realization of EMIC-ETIC perspective?
 3. What implications can be derived from the presence/absence of realization of EMIC-ETIC perspective on the V-M-O at the School of Education of AU Pasay Campus?
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METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive design of research that includes data collecting, analyzing, and tabulating about the prevailing perspectives of the respondents. It mainly aimed to determine and examine the EMIC and ETIC perspectives of the parents and faculty members on the Vision-Mission-Objective of the School of Education, Arellano University-Jose Abad Santos Campus.

The respondents of this study were selected using non-probability sampling technique which is the convenience sampling. They are composed of 50 parents and 14 faculty members of the School of Education, AU-JAS Campus. The parent-respondents must have a child who is currently enrolled during the 1st Semester, school year 2022-2023 and presently residing in Metro Manila. The faculty-respondents are currently teaching in the college with at least 12 units of teaching load. The convenience sampling was used because of the ease of availability of the sample in the case of parent-respondents.

The study utilized the VMO Assessment Tool of Arellano University. It is composed of 25-item key result areas or indicators of the study that determine the EMIC and ETIC perspective of the parents and faculty members on the Vision-Mission-Objective of the School of Education.

To answer specific questions, the researchers used statistical formulas as follows:
Weighted mean – this was used to determine the extent of realization of the V-M-O from EMIC-ETIC Perspective.

T-test will be used to test if significant difference exists in case there is absence of realization of EMIC-ETIC Perspective.

RESULTS

Table 1

Extent of Realization of the V-M-O from EMIC-ETIC Perspective

KEY RESULTS AREAS/INDICATORS	Faculty		Parent		Total	
	WM	Description	WM	Description	WM	Description
The VMO of the School of Education:						
1. Inculcates nationalism. (Paghubog ng nasyonalismo.)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.08	Realized	3.41	Realized
2. Promotes ethical leadership. (Pagpapaangat ng Etikal na Pamumuno.)	3.82	Fully Realized	3.00	Realized	3.41	Realized
3. Promotes inclusive education. (Pagtatanghal ng Inklusibong Edukasyon.)	3.82	Fully Realized	3.13	Realized	3.48	Realized
4. Provides relevant and pragmatic knowledge and skill to adopt with local and global issues and trends. (Pagbibigay ng kahalagahan at pragmatikang kaalaman at kasanayan upang maiangkop sa lokal at global na isyung napapanahon.)	3.45	Realized	3.17	Realized	3.31	Realized
5. Promotes local and regional collaborations. (Pagbabatid ng lokal at global na kolaborasyon.)	3.45	Realized	2.79	Realized	3.12	Realized
6. Promotes peace and respect for human rights. (Pagtatanghal ng kapayapaan at paggalang sa karapatang pantao.)	3.82	Fully Realized	3.17	Realized	3.50	Fully Realized
7. Promotes concern for the natural environment. (Paghahatid kaalaman sa pagmamalasakit sa kalikasan at kapaligiran.)	3.64	Fully Realized	3.29	Realized	3.47	Realized
8. Reflects the teaching of desirable values for community building. (Paglilimi sa pagtuturo ng karapat-dapat na pagpapahalaga sa pabuo ng lipunan.)	3.82	Fully Realized	3.29	Realized	3.59	Fully Realized
9. Integrates familial and community knowledge and values in the reformulation of the curriculum. (Isinasama ang karunungan pang-pamilya at panlipunan at pagpapahalaga sa pagbuo ng kurikulum.)	3.82	Fully Realized	3.08	Realized	3.45	Realized
10. Reflects tolerance of diverse views, beliefs, genders, interests, and experiences of stakeholders. (Sinasalamin ang pagpaparaya ng magkakaibang pananaw, paniniwala, kasarian, at karanasan ng mga stakeholder/kasapi.)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.04	Realized	3.39	Realized
11. Promotes school-community partnership. (Nagtatanghal ng partnersyip ng paaralan at komunidad.)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.08	Realized	3.39	Realized
12. Develops one's capacity to participate in a democratic community. (Pagpapaunlad sa kakayahan upang makilahok sa isang malayang lipunan.)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.09	Realized	3.41	Realized
13. Inculcates sense of pride in one's alma mater. (Pagpapahalaga ng pagbibigay-papuri/pagmamalaki sa Alma Mater.)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.38	Realized	3.56	Fully Realized
14. Strengthens spirit of collective identity and solidarity.	3.82	Fully Realized	3.29	Realized	3.56	Fully Realized

(Pagpapalakas sa diwa ng kolektibong pag-kakakilanlan at pagkakaisa.)						
15. Facilitates collective decision making. (Pinapagana ang kolektibong paggawa ng desisyon.)	3.55	Fully Realized	2.96	Realized	3.26	Realized
16. Implements culturally sensitive curriculum. (Nagpapatupad ng kurikulum na sensitibo sa kultura.)	3.64	Fully Realized	3.08	Realized	3.36	Realized
17. Provides opportunities for personal and professional development. (Naglalaan ng oportunidad sa pagpapaunlad ng personal at propesyonal na aspeto.)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.08	Realized	3.41	Realized
18. Affirms one's self worth and dignity. (Pinagtatibay ang halaga ng sarili at dignidad ng isang tao.)	3.82	Fully Realized	3.25	Realized	3.54	Fully Realized
19. Reflects the needs, values, experiences, and aspirations of stakeholders. (Sinasalamin ang mga pangangailangan, halaga, karanasan, at adhikain ng mga stakeholder/kasapi.)	3.64	Fully Realized	3.04	Realized	3.34	Realized
20. Instills institutional values to strengthen one's disposition. (Inilalagay sa isipan ang pag-uugaling institusyunal upang palakasin ang sariling disposisyon.)	3.73	Fully Realized	2.96	Realized	3.35	Realized
21. Provides good quality teaching and learning for its students. (Pagbibigay ng kalidad na pagtuturo at pagkatuto para sa mga mag-aaral.)	3.64	Fully Realized	3.00	Realized	3.32	Realized
22. Stirs personal and collective interest to produce knowledge and share innovations. (Paglalahok ng personal at kolektibong interes upang magbunga ng karunungan at maiging na inobasyon.)	3.55	Fully Realized	3.00	Realized	3.28	Realized
23. Develops entrepreneurial values, knowledge, and skills. (Bumubuo ng entreprenyural na pagpapahalaga, karunungan at kasanayan)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.21	Realized	3.47	Realized
24. Develops research values, knowledge, and skills. (Paghuhubog ng pagpapahalaga sa pananaliksik, karunungan/kaalaman at kasanayan)	3.64	Fully Realized	3.25	Realized	3.45	Realized
25. Develops critical knowledge for social advocacy and participation. (Bumubuo ng kritikal na kaalaman para sa panlipunang adbokasiya at pakikilahok)	3.73	Fully Realized	3.21	Realized	3.47	Realized
GRAND WEIGHTED MEAN	3.70	Fully Realized	3.12	Realized	3.41	Realized

DISCUSSION

An analysis of the data revealed that the V-M-O was fully realized as evaluated by the teachers with a grand weighted mean of 3.70. This shows that the teachers believed that the V-M-O promotes ethical leadership, inclusive education and peace and respect for human rights as shown by the computed weighted mean of 3.82. Likewise, the teachers were aware that the school reflects the teaching of desirable values for

community building as confirmed by the weighted mean of 3.82 and interpreted as fully realized. According to teachers, it can be seen in the Arellano University core values which are competence, humility, integrity, equity, fortitude and stewardship. They added that these values were incorporated in the curriculum and they also include it in their lessons whenever possible. The school was also strong in terms of promoting school-community partnership according to teachers as revealed by the computed weighted mean of 3.73 and interpreted as fully realized. The teachers said that Arellano University is always participating in different community outreach program such as Bamboo planting in Pangil, Laguna, carabao propagation in San Miguel, Bulacan, and other community programs in adopted barangays in Pasay City and Cavite.

A second look from the table revealed that the V-M-O of Arellano University was realized as shown by the grand weighted mean of 3.12 based on the evaluation of the parents. Inculcates sense of pride in one's Alma mater got the highest weighted mean of 3.29 interpreted as realized. The parents said that their children were very proud of their school which is Arellano University. According to the data, the parents assessed that the school realized the promotion of concern for the natural environment (WM = 3.29), reflects the teaching of desirable values for community building (WM = 3.29), and strengthens spirit of collective identity and solidarity (WM = 3.29). All these items according to them were transpired in the V-M-O of School of Education, Arellano University.

Generally, the V-M-O of School of Education, Arellano University was realized as shown by the total grand weighted mean of 3.42. Further analysis of the data revealed that teaching of desirable values for community building got the highest total weighted mean of 3.59, interpreted as fully realized. This was followed by inculcating sense of pride in one's Alma mater and strengthening spirit of collective identity and solidarity which both got the total weighted mean of 3.56. Similarly, affirms one's self worth and dignity (WM = 3.54) and promotes peace and respect for human rights (WM = 3.50) were also rated as fully realized.

The data shows that both faculty and teachers were aware that the items listed above were all present in the Vision-Mission-Objectives of Arellano University.

According to the findings of the preceding study, university stakeholders, such as students and professors, are aware of the university's vision, mission, goals, and objectives, and that these students and professors understand and accept these statements, as well as the responsibility for realizing such objectives in their own capacities (Castillo, 2014). Another study found that university constituents are aware of and interested in the basic ideas presented in their VMGOs (Salom & Florendo, 2013). Parents/alumnae and other stakeholders have clearly demonstrated a high degree of awareness, acceptance, and understanding of the university's VMGO (Manapsal, 2016).

Conclusions

The Vision-Mission-Objectives of Arellano University was either fully realized or realized and there was no evidence that there is an absence of realization of this V-M-O in the EMIC-ETIC perspective. Hence, there is no difference in the respondents' perspective since there was no evidence that there is an absence of the items in V-M-O of Arellano University.

Recommendations

Although, the presence of realization of EMIC-ETIC perspective on the V-M-O of the School of Education, Arellano University was noted from the results of this study, the following recommendations which were culled from the answers of the respondents in the open-ended questions will be considered to improve its services to the clientele:

1) The university should be able to communicate and authorize its vision and mission through activities that shall involve all stakeholders. These activities shall be funded well to ensure sustainability;

2) The University needs to make sure that all their facilities are in good shape and maintain cleanliness and order in the school grounds;

3) There is no unity with other students who come from different departments. Some programs/activities should be done where all first-year students need to attend so that they may be familiarized with one another and what courses can be found here;

4) Feedback from the stakeholders on the services of different offices must be provided;

5) Since we are in the 21st century and we have 21st century learners/students, we need to be more innovative. Let the student experience how innovations and technologies will help them to become more competitive outside the school; and

6) The university can improve its community service by intensifying its relationship to the nearby barangay through outreach program such as feeding and gift-giving to the poor. The university had already a project of adopt a community but in a far way area. They said that charity begins at home and within reach.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

We, Dr. Marlowe Louis F. Fabunan, Dr. Joana Marie Carina M. Gabunilas, Dr. Archieval A. Rodriguez and Prof. Rosalia T. Pastrana, thus declare that all information gathered and made available in this study was received with the consent of the respondents. They were appropriately informed and given the option to withdraw from the study at any time. The respondents' anonymity was maintained, they were not subjected to any form of harm, there was no conflict of interest in the study's conduct, plagiarism was strictly

avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were used purely for research.

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